

Electronic Banking and Customers Satisfaction in Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between electronic banking and customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The research explores the factors that contribute to customers' satisfaction with electronic banking services and their impact on overall customer experience and loyalty over the period; 2012 to 2021. The focus was on selected electronic banking products-Mobile payments, Automated teller machine (ATM), Internet banking (WEB) and Point of sale (POS) transactions, while customer satisfaction was measured by Return on Assets as a result of increased customer patronage and profitability. The Study adopts ex post facto research design. Secondary data were collected through annual reports and statistical bulletin of Central Bank of Nigeria within the stated period and analyzed quantitatively. The formulated hypotheses were tested using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) inferential statistical tool to determine the effect of E-banking on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The results indicated that e-banking in the aggregate has a positive but insignificant effect on customers' satisfaction in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Conclusively, the recommendations from this study highlighted the importance of enhancing service quality, embracing digital banking technologies and improving the overall infrastructure to foster a more efficient and customer-centric banking sector.

Keywords: ATM, Customer satisfaction, Electronic banking, Mobile banking, Point of sale

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Introduction

Electronic banking (E-banking) refers to the process of conducting financial transactions and managing banking activities through electronic channels, primarily over the internet. It allows individuals and businesses to access and perform various banking services remotely, using electronic devices such as computers, smart phones or tablets. It provides a convenient and efficient way to carry out a wide range of financial activities without the need for physical visits to a bank branch.

The nascent advances in technology seen around the world have eliminated the traditional manual banking system and brought about a paradigm shift in banking to the extent that banks are using

internet technologies to improve efficiency and scale up the provision of a wide range of value-added products and services (Oyewole et al, 2013; Oyedokun, & Umar, 2017). Consequently, Nigerian banks, especially commercial ones, now identify electronic banking as a unique means of differentiating themselves from their rivalries by investing in complicated expertise (Ovia, 2001).

Electronic banking has become a central concept in the banking industry due to its ability to increase operational efficiency and enhance customer satisfaction. The impact of this technology on commerce cannot be denied, especially in relation to trade. The development in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a major turning point in the way business is conducted in every sector of the economy globally. Amongst the leading customers who embraced ICT, banks remain at the very top of the list. Over the years, banks have tailored their services to involve more digital mediums as development in the trends of technology progresses. Electronic banking offers multiple banking activities through telecommunication and electronic networks for the purpose of delivering value-added products and quality services to its esteemed customers. Amongst these services that can be performed through electronic mediums include transfer of funds, opening of accounts, payment of bills, etc. Essentially, E-banking includes mobile banking, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), online banking, Point of Sales (POS), credit cards and debit cards (Ariyasena & Jayarathne, 2019; Viko, Nnorom, & Oyedokun, 2018). At the moment, banking products continue to evolve in conjunction with technological innovations. Before, customers always had to go to the banking hall to perform transactions like deposit of money or withdrawal of money at the bank's counter, however these activities can be accomplished anywhere through electronic banking mediums and channels.

The usage of e-banking products aims to reduce transaction costs, decongesting the banking premises by reducing the number of hours customers spend in the banking hall, also saving more time for both the banks and customers while maximizing efficiency in service rendered (Osly, 2020). Despite the significant advancements in e-banking and the adoption of various e-banking services by deposit money banks in Nigeria, customer satisfaction remains a critical issue. Customer satisfaction in the context of electronic banking is influenced by various factors, including the availability, reliability, and security of e-banking services. While e-banking offers numerous benefits such as convenience, speed, and accessibility, several challenges persist that affect the overall satisfaction of customers. These challenges include frequent network failures, security concerns related to online transactions, and inadequate customer support services. There has been serious and uncontrollable lamentation from members of the public and bankers about its shortcomings that hinder banking operations in that if nothing is done to curtail the excesses, it might hinder the progress of banks (Oyedokun, Mohammed, & Adeyemo, 2019).

Understanding the relationship between E-banking and customer satisfaction is crucial for deposit money banks in Nigeria. High levels of customer satisfaction can lead to increased customer loyalty, positive word-of-mouth, and ultimately, improved profitability. Conversely, dissatisfaction can result in customer attrition and a negative reputation.

It is against this background that this study was designed to examine the impact of electronic banking on the customer satisfaction in money deposit banks in Nigeria with the following specific objectives; to explore the impact of mobile banking, online banking, automatic teller machine and point of sale on return on assets of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Customer Support

Customer support is an important component of the quality of service offered by electronic banking platforms, significantly influencing customer satisfaction. It involves a range of activities, including technical assistance, handling inquiries, resolving transaction-related issues, and providing guidance on using various e-banking services. Effective customer support ensures that customers can quickly and efficiently resolve any problems they encounter, thereby maintaining a positive perception of the bank and its services. It is a vital dimension of service quality, which directly impacts customer satisfaction (Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019; Ibekwe, 2021). The quality of customer support services can determine whether customers perceive their interactions with the bank as positive or negative. In e-banking, interactions are often remote and mediated by technology; the availability and effectiveness of customer support become even more crucial.

The speed at which customer support responds to inquiries and resolves issues is a critical factor in customer satisfaction. Long waiting times and delays in problem resolution can lead to frustration and dissatisfaction. Studies have shown that prompt responses from customer support can significantly enhance customer satisfaction (Oyedokun, Ojo, & Ugoh, 2020; Ibekwe, 2021). The availability of customer support services, such as 24/7 helplines, live chat options, and comprehensive Frequently Ask Questions (FAQs) ensures that customers can access help whenever they need it.

Empirical studies support the critical role of customer support in driving customer satisfaction in e-banking. A study found that customer support is one of the significant determinants of customer satisfaction in the banking sector. Their research highlighted that effective customer support leads to increased customer trust, loyalty, and overall satisfaction with the bank (Oyedokun, Orenuga, & Adeolu-Akande, 2021; Ugbede, 2021).

Similarly, research emphasized the importance of responsiveness and reliability of customer support services in shaping customer perceptions of e-banking quality. Their findings suggest that banks that invest in efficient and responsive customer support systems are more likely to achieve higher levels of customer satisfaction (Oyedokun, Babajide, & Adeyemo, 2021; Madugba, 2021).

Customer Feedback and Complaint Handling

Customer feedback refers to the information provided by customers about their experiences and perceptions of e-banking services. Complaint handling involves the processes and practices that banks use to address and resolve customer complaints. Both elements are important because they offer valuable insights into customer needs and expectations, allowing banks to improve their services and enhance customer satisfaction.

Effective complaint handling is a main component of service recovery, which directly impacts customer satisfaction and loyalty (Monje-Amor, 2020). Interactions are often virtual in e-banking; the ability to efficiently gather, analyze, and respond to customer feedback and complaints is crucial for maintaining a positive customer experience.

Providing multiple and easily accessible channels for customers to give feedback and lodge complaints is essential. These channels can include online forms, email, chat bots, social media, and telephone support. Accessible feedback mechanisms ensure that customers can conveniently express their concerns and suggestions. Research highlights that the availability of multiple feedback channels is positively correlated with customer satisfaction (Paais, 2020). The speed at which banks respond to customer feedback and resolve complaints significantly affects customer satisfaction. Prompt responses show customers that the bank values their input and is committed to addressing their concerns. Studies have shown that timely complaint resolution is a critical determinant of customer satisfaction and loyalty (Santos, 2020). The effectiveness of the solutions provided to make customer complaints is crucial.

Reliability

Reliability in e-banking refers to the consistency and dependability of the banking services provided through electronic channels. It encompasses several dimensions, including system uptime, accuracy of transactions, and the consistency of service delivery. It is important because it directly affects customers' trust and confidence in the bank's ability to manage their financial transactions securely and accurately. It is the most critical dimension of service quality and significantly impacts customer satisfaction (Yao et al, 2021). It ensures that customers can consistently perform banking transactions without errors or interruptions, thereby enhancing their overall experience and satisfaction.

The availability of the e-banking system is a fundamental aspect of reliability. Customers expect the system to be operational and accessible whenever they need to perform transactions. High system uptime ensures that customers can rely on the e-banking platform for their financial needs. Research highlights that system availability is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction in online banking (Al-Saqqa et al, 2020). Accuracy in processing transactions is critical for reliability. Customers need to trust that their transactions, whether it is transfers, payments, or account updates, will be executed correctly and promptly. Inaccuracies can lead to financial losses and erode trust, negatively impacting customer satisfaction. Studies emphasize that transaction accuracy is essential for building customer trust and satisfaction (Branicki, 2020). Consistent service delivery means that customers experience the same level of service quality every time they use the e-banking platform. Inconsistencies can lead to frustration and dissatisfaction. Ensuring consistent performance across different service interactions is crucial for maintaining high customer satisfaction levels (Madaio et al, 2020).

Usability of Services

Usability refers to the ease with which customers can navigate and use the online banking services provided by financial institutions. It includes the design of the user interface, the intuitiveness of the navigation, the clarity of instructions, and the overall user experience. It is important because it directly impacts on how customers perceive the e-banking service and their satisfaction with it.

Usability is defined by five attributes, namely, learnability, efficiency, memorability, errors, and satisfaction (Kip et al, 2020). These attributes are essential for ensuring that customers can easily access and effectively use e-banking services. High usability leads to a more enjoyable and satisfying user experience, which is important for customer retention and loyalty. A user-friendly navigation system is essential for ensuring that customers can easily find the information and

services they need. This includes clear menus, logical organization of contents, and intuitive navigation paths. Research highlights that ease of navigation significantly affects customer satisfaction in online banking (Oyedokun & Adewuyi, 2022; Ritala, 2024). The design of the user interface (UI) plays a critical role in usability. A well-designed UI is visually appealing, easy to understand, and consistent across different sections of the e-banking platform. Studies have shown that a well-designed UI enhances the overall user experience and satisfaction (Janssen, 2020). Clear instructions and information are essential for guiding customers through various tasks on the e-banking platform. This includes providing concise and understandable instructions for transactions help sections, and FAQs. Research indicates that the clarity of information positively influences customer satisfaction and trust in e-banking services (Hickey, 2022).

Convenience

As financial institutions increasingly rely on digital platforms to deliver their services, the convenience of these platforms becomes a significant factor influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty. Convenience in e-banking refers to the ease and efficiency with which customers can conduct their banking transactions using electronic platforms. It encompasses several dimensions, including ease of access, speed of transactions, availability of services, and flexibility. It is particularly important in e-banking because it directly affects the customer experience and their perception of the bank's service quality. It is a multidimensional construct that significantly impacts customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions (Davis, 1989). Convenience can enhance customer satisfaction by providing a seamless, time-saving, and user-friendly banking experience. The ability to access banking services anytime and anywhere, without the need to visit a physical branch, is a major advantage of e-banking.

The ability to access e-banking services effortlessly from various devices, such as computers, smartphones, and tablets, is a critical aspect of convenience. Platforms that are easily accessible and user-friendly tend to enhance customer satisfaction. Studies have shown that ease of access is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction in e-banking (Madugba, 2021). The efficiency and speed at which transactions are processed play a crucial role in customer satisfaction. Customers prefer e-banking platforms that allow them to complete transactions quickly and without unnecessary delays. Research found that the speed of service delivery is a major factor influencing customer satisfaction in online banking (Korpelainen, 2011). The availability of a wide range of banking services online, such as fund transfers, bill payments, account management, and loan applications, contributes to convenience. Customers value the ability to perform various banking activities without having to visit a physical branch. The breadth of services available online is positively correlated with customer satisfaction (Taiwo, 2016).

Trust and Confidence

Trust and confidence are fundamental indicators of customer satisfaction in electronic banking. Trust and confidence in e-banking refer to customers' belief in the reliability, security, and integrity of the e-banking services provided by their financial institutions. These factors are crucial because they directly affect customers' willingness to engage with and use e-banking platforms. Trust reduces the perceived risk associated with online transactions and enhances the overall customer experience. Trust is a key determinant of customer satisfaction in online services (Chukwu et al,

2021; Oyedokun, & Osho, 2023). Trust encompasses several dimensions, including the bank's ability to protect customer data, the accuracy of transactions, and the overall dependability of the e-banking system. Confidence, closely related to trust, refers to the customers' assurance that the bank will fulfill its promises and provide secure, reliable services.

The perception of robust security measures is fundamental to building trust and confidence in e-banking. Customers need to believe that their personal and financial information is protected against unauthorized access and cyber threats. Research highlights that perceived security significantly impacts trust and customer satisfaction in online banking (Reddy, 2021; Oyedokun, & Adeyemi, Adewumi, 2023). Ensuring the privacy of customer information is another critical aspect of trust. Banks must implement strict privacy policies and practices to protect customer data. Studies have shown that concerns about privacy can negatively affect customer trust and satisfaction if not adequately addressed (Tinuoye, 2021). The reliability of e-banking services, including the accuracy of transactions and the availability of the platform, is crucial for trust. Customers need to be confident that the e-banking system will perform consistently without errors or downtime. Research indicates that reliability is a key factor in building trust and confidence in online banking (Ueda, 2020; Oyedokun & Durowaiye, 2022).

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Technology Acceptance Model. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed to elucidate the recognition of information Technology for carrying out diverse undertakings and to forecast the acceptance of online banking (Davis, 1989). The theory establishes that the user's acceptance of a new information system is dependent on the user's perception about the system and determined by an individual's intention to use the systems. The two philosophies that define users' intentions are as follows; "perceived ease of use of technology and perceived advantages of using the technology in terms of its usefulness are the basic factors that influence an individual's acceptance of an information system". Perceived usefulness is the degree to which an individual believes that the use of a system will increase his/her general performance in relation to its productivity and effectiveness. The productivity and effectiveness are the ability of a system to be timesaving and to be of comparative advantage to individual set goals in relations of work. Perceived ease of use on the other hand is the point to which an individual believes that the smallest or no effort at all is required for usage of a certain system in relationships to both physical effort and mental and simplicity of learning how to practice the system (Davis, 1989). In addition, Davis further argues that "perceived ease of use" influences perceived usefulness.

Empirical Review

Nwekpa, Djobissie, Chukwuma and Ezezue (2020) carried out research on the influence of e-banking on customer satisfaction: a study of Fidelity Bank Plc. The purpose was to evaluate the influence of online credit card payment system on customer satisfaction and assess the influence of electronic e-cash system on customer satisfaction. The study employed survey research design and sampled forty-one respondents. Hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis. The findings revealed that there is a significant effect of the online credit card payment system on customer satisfaction at Fidelity Bank Plc. It equally showed that there is a

significant effect of the electronic e-cash system on customer satisfaction at Fidelity Bank Plc. Based on this, it was recommended that banks are required to ensure that the challenges of electronic banking system are solved totally or brought down to minimum. The problem of erratic power supply should be worked on so that customers that wish to use bank ATM can do so without fear of their being debited or customer cards being trapped. Inverters should be put in place to serve this purpose 24 hours. Also, banks should organize seminars/workshops for customers to bring awareness of electronic banking to people in the rural area and illiterate customers who find it difficult to make use of their ATMs for transactions.

Ijeoma, Akujor and Mbah (2020) examined the impact of electronic banking on customer satisfaction in commercial banks in Imo State. The study used primary data; the instrument used in gathering data was questionnaires. The statistical tool of analysis is the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Techniques. The result revealed that there is a positive relationship between electronic banking and customer satisfaction at United Bank for Africa Plc., Access Bank Ltd and Keystone Bank Ltd. It also revealed that there is a positive relationship between Automated Teller Machine and Mobile Banking and customer satisfaction at United Bank for Africa Plc., Access Bank Ltd and Keystone Bank Ltd. Moreover, the study shows that there is a negative relationship between the point of sale and customer satisfaction in the three (3) banks. This implies that the increase in charges levied on those electronic banking systems will have a corresponding decrease in customer satisfaction and vice versa. The study therefore recommends that banks should improve continuously in the advance of Automated Teller Machine for speedy transaction by customers, financial institutions (banks) and non-financial institutions should endeavor to make available POS machines at a minimal cost to some small business outlets to help in the achievement of cashless economy.

Asuquo (2020) conducted a study in Rivers State, Nigeria to examine the influence of electronic banking services on customers' satisfaction in selected deposit money banks. Three hundred and seven (307) copies of questionnaire were utilized to elicit the required information from the customers and staff of four (4) systematically important (too big to fail) banks and eight (8) national banks. The data gathered focused mainly on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, nature and types of customers' complaints regarding electronic banking and other challenges that influence effective implementation of electronic banking services as perceived by the bank staff. A combination of descriptive and inferential statistics was employed as techniques for data analysis. The findings revealed that customers' complaints regarding electronic banking include debiting of their accounts by the ATM without payment, non-availability of cash at the ATM, resolution of disputes on the electronic banking products and trapping of customer's card by the ATM. Aside the customers' complaints, it was equally found that the bank staff identified network failure, limited personnel, mishandling of the naira note and CBN's directive on trapped cards as other key challenges that obstruct effective implementation of electronic banking services.

Anyadighibe, Awara and Esu (2022) examined service quality automation and customer satisfaction of deposit money banks conducted, findings revealed that consistency (accuracy, dependability and availability), queue management (prompt service and time saving), safety (security, privacy, trust, confidence), and quality service enjoyment (convenience, ease of use, usefulness, easy access and minimal cost) of DMBs automation all had positive effect on customer satisfaction. It was recommended that DMBs should ensure that bank automation transactions are accurate (correct statement of account) and dependable (no absence of network, ATM dispensing

new note and not out of cash or order) at all times to customers. Also, DMBs should provide fast automation for cash transfer and withdrawal; and ensure that no reduction in balance without payment in electronic banking transactions to customers in order to guarantee customers’ trust. Furthermore, they should provide customers with ease of use and easy accessibility on electronic banking transactions.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study employed ex post facto research design. Secondary data were collected through annual reports and statistical bulletin of Central Bank of Nigeria over the period of 2012 to 2021. The study analyzed the co-movement of the value of mobile banking, online banking, automated teller machine and point of sales of deposit money banks in Nigeria within the stated period with the return on assets of a select few deposit money banks in Nigeria; Access Bank PLC, Zenith Bank PLC and United Bank for Africa PLC meaning. Hypotheses were tested using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) inferential statistical tool to determine the effect of e-banking on customers’ satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Results and Presentation of Data

Descriptive statistics of all the variables used in the study were reported in Table 1. The model variable comprises of return on assets (ROA), amount of mobile banking services (MB), Automated teller machine (ATM), online banking (OB), and point of sales (POS). These variables were used in achieving the objectives of the study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	ROA	ATM	MB	OB	POS
Mean	5.256357	4.77E+12	2.01E+12	2.63E+13	1.21E+12
Median	5.326574	4.48E+12	8.57E+11	1.58E+11	6.60E+11
Maximum	6.832933	1.20E+13	9.43E+12	2.36E+14	3.20E+12
Minimum	4.091646	2.82E+11	3.15E+10	3.16E+10	4.85E+10
Std. Dev.	0.788555	3.19E+12	2.99E+12	7.40E+13	1.17E+12
Skewness	0.255953	0.964425	1.791349	2.610593	0.680360
Kurtosis	3.100481	3.850112	4.860455	7.923097	1.851122
Jarque-Bera	0.113394	1.851312	6.790422	21.45736	1.321449

Probability	0.944880	0.396271	0.033533	0.000022	0.516477
Sum	52.56357	4.77E+13	2.01E+13	2.63E+14	1.21E+13
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.596373	9.17E+25	8.06E+25	4.93E+28	1.24E+25
Observations	10	10	10	10	10

Source: E-view Version 10.0 2024

The outcome of descriptive statistics in Table 1 indicates that 5.256357, 4,770,000,000,000, 2,010,000,000,000, 26,300,000,000,000 and 1,210,000,000,000 were the average value of ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS. The median amount of ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS were; 5.326574, 4480000000000, 857000000000, 158000000000 and 660000000000 respectively. The maximum value of the variables ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS were; 6.832933, 12000000000,000, 9430000000000, 23600000000000 and 3200000000000 while the minimum values were; 4.091646, 282000000000, 31500000000, 31600000000 and 48500000000 respectively. The standard deviation showed 0.788555, 3190000000000, 2990000000000, 7400000000000 and 1170000000000 for ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS. The Skewness showed 0.255953, 0.964425, 1.791349, 2.610593 and 0.680360 for ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS. The Kurtosis showed 3.100481, 3.850112, 4.860455, 7.923097 and 1.851122 for ROA, MB, ATM, OB and POS. The Jarque-Bera test for normality showed that none of the variables were not normally distributed.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis: Ordinary

Correlation						
Probability		ROA	ATM	MB	OB	POS
ROA		1.000000				

ATM		-0.358747	1.000000			
		0.3087	-----			
MB		-0.585458	0.873989	1.000000		
		0.0754	0.0009	-----		
OB		-0.561603	0.747888	0.863333	1.000000	
		0.0911	0.0129	0.0013	-----	
POS		-0.461274	0.791412	0.814930	0.461311	1.000000
		0.1796	0.0064	0.0041	0.1796	-----

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

The result of the correlation is reported in Table 2. It can be deduced from the correlation analysis that low level correlation was observed among the explanatory variables. This implies that there is less likelihood of encountering multicollinearity problems which may understate or overstate standard errors and thereby lead to wrong inference about the behavior of the variable.

Table 3: Cross-Sectional Unit Root Test

Variables	Level		1 st difference	
	C	C & T	C	C & T
MB	0.0598	0.0032	0.0003	0.0006
ATM	0.0006	0.0004	0.0004	0.0002
OB	1.0000	-	-	-
POS	0.0006	0.0002	0.0016	0.0065
ROA	0.2914	0.3069	0.0163	0.0235

Source: E- view Version 10.0 2024

Unit Root determines order of integration of variables prior to model estimation. This is important to avoid the problem of lack of efficiency and inconsistency of model estimates. The study adopts Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test. The result of the test in Table 3 shows that all variables were stationary at first difference, the outcome informed the decision of the study to adopt Ordinary Least Square (OLS).

Table 4: Regression Estimate

Dependent Variable: ROA				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.490044	5.313570	0.845014	0.4367
LATM	0.326102	0.171537	1.901060	0.1157
LMB	-0.964405	0.600781	-1.605253	0.1693
LOB	0.004850	0.113860	0.042596	0.9677
LPOS	0.645818	0.593866	1.087480	0.3264
R-squared	0.871040	Mean dependent var		5.256357
Adjusted R-squared	0.767872	S.D. dependent var		0.788555
S.E. of regression	0.379923	Akaike info criterion		1.209159
Sum squared resid	0.721709	Schwarz criterion		1.360451
Log likelihood	-1.045794	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.043191
F-statistic	8.442917	Durbin-Watson stat		2.138479
Prob (F-statistic)	0.018977			

Source: E-View Version 10.0 2024

Hypotheses Testing

H0₁: Mobile banking has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H0₂: Online banking does not significantly influence customer satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H0₃: Automated Teller Machines does not significantly impact customer satisfaction with electronic banking services in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H0₄: Point of Sales systems do not significantly affect customer satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Effect of mobile banking on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria

The variable of mobile banking exhibited statistical insignificant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria ($t=-1.605253$, $p>0.05$). The coefficient of mobile banking shows that return on assets of banking in Nigeria falls in average of (-0.964405) with a unit increase in revenue from mobile banking. The adoption of mobile banking has not contributed significantly to the operation of banks. Mobile banking reduces the cost of banking; it reduces the number of employees needed to render banking services in the country.

Influence of online banking on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria

The online banking (OB) has no significant influence on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria ($t=0.042596$, $p>0.05$). Online banking is not popular among the populace in the country. Many customers of the bank are not literate and not interested in activating their online banking application.

Effect of automated teller machines on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria

Automated Teller Machines has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria ($t=1.901060$, $p>0.05$). This implies that the rise in the value of ATM did not lead to the rise in return of assets of banks.

Outcome of point of sales on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria

Point of Sales has no significant effects on customers' satisfaction deposit money banks in Nigeria ($t=1.087480$, $p>0.05$). The coefficient of point of sales shows that return on assets of banks in Nigeria rises in average of 0.645818 with a unit increase in revenue from point of sales. Introduction of Point of Sales in Nigeria has led to reduction in cost of funds, reduced excessive pressure on banking facilities.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one states that; mobile banking has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. From Table 4, the t-statistic of -1.605253 is less than the critical value (± 1.96 , 95% confidence level), and the p-value is greater than 0.05. This indicates that there is not enough statistical evidence to suggest a significant relationship between mobile banking and customer satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The negative coefficient of -0.964405 suggests that an increase in revenue from mobile banking is associated with a decrease in return on assets, implying that mobile banking has not significantly improved bank performance or customer satisfaction. Also, while mobile banking reduces operational costs and staffing needs, this may not translate directly to enhanced customer satisfaction. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we accept the hypothesis that mobile banking has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Hypothesis two put forward that; online banking has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The t-statistic of 0.042596 in Table 4 is extremely close to zero, and the p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating that online banking has no statistically significant effect on customer satisfaction in Nigerian banks. The low t-statistic suggests that the mean difference between the observed data and the null hypothesis is negligible. Furthermore, the study revealed that online banking is not widely adopted due to literacy challenges and lack of interest in activating online banking services among the population. This lack of adoption could be a main factor in the absence of significant effects on customer satisfaction. Given the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, we accept the hypothesis that online banking has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Hypothesis three is that; automated teller machines have no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The t-statistic of 1.901060 in Table 4 is close to the typical threshold of ± 1.96 used for a 95% confidence level. However, it is still slightly below this threshold, indicating that the effect of ATMs on customer satisfaction is not statistically significant at the 95% confidence level. The p-value is greater than 0.05, which further indicates that the effect of ATMs on customer satisfaction is not statistically significant. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we accept the hypothesis that automated teller machines have no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Hypothesis four states that; point of sales systems has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. From Table 4, the t-statistic of 1.087480 is below the critical threshold of ± 1.96 , indicating a lack of statistical significance in the effect of POS systems on customer satisfaction. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result indicates that POS systems do not have a statistically significant effect on customer satisfaction. The positive coefficient of 0.645818 suggests that there might be a positive relationship between POS revenue and the return on assets of banks. However, this relationship is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant in terms of affecting customer satisfaction. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we accept the hypothesis that point of sales systems has no significant effect on customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has shown that none of the electronic banking channels adopted has variables in the study; (mobile banking, point of sales, automated teller machine, online banking) have improved customers' satisfaction in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study consequently infers that spending money on e-banking may not necessarily improve performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, judicious use and management of banks' resources increase in customer base and customer retention coupled with excellent service delivery will contribute meaningfully to banks' performance. Net profit after interest and tax serves as the major factors representing deposit money banks in Nigeria

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- i. Managements of deposit money banks should provide service excellence and improved service quality to their esteemed customers.
- ii. There's a need to enhance customer awareness and education about mobile and online banking benefits. Improving user experience and ensuring these technologies align more closely with customer needs and preferences could help increase adoption rates and satisfaction levels.
- iii. The managers of banks need to always train customers with regard to electronic banking facilities and the provision of easy to use and customer interactive features in electronic banking equipment.
- iv. Further investigation into specific barriers that prevent customers from fully utilizing online and mobile banking services is crucial. This could involve qualitative research methods, such as surveys or interviews, to understand customer perceptions and potential hurdles.

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